

THE VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH TEMPERATURE OF NON-AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF WEAK ELECTROLYTES

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The variation of specific conductivity with temperature has been studied. It has been observed that for the solutions of different organic acids in methyl alcohol, the plot of $\mu-t$ is a straight line. But for a few solutions where the viscosity is high the plot of $\mu-t$ is not a straight line and therefore these solutions do not obey Walden's equation (1) and probably these solutions obey the equation of Kohlrausch (2). Solutions of butyl and propyl alcohols and acetone obey the equation (1) where the conductivity is high, otherwise they obey the equation (2). It has been observed that in the case of substituted benzoic acids the conductivity of the substituted compound follows the order: $\text{NH}_2 > \text{NO}_2 > \text{OH}$ group.

Variation of molecular conductivity of organic acids in ethyl alcohol with temperature has been studied by Wiesel, Jones and Wightman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 2243). Hunt and Briscoe (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 1495) found several interesting results regarding the structure of the acid and the conductivity in the case of solutions of various substituted benzoic acids in ethyl alcohol. In the present paper the variation of specific conductivity with temperature of the solutions of weak electrolytes in methyl, propyl and butyl alcohols and acetone has been studied and the validity of the equations of Walden and Kohlrausch has been tested. Molecular conductivity of the solutions could not be determined as the solutions taken were highly concentrated and supersaturated, and hence density could not be accurately determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the solutes and the solvents from Kahlbaum and B. D. H. were purified by the standard methods and the solutes were dried in a vacuum desiccator.

We have used the Kohlrausch bridge assembly consisting of a calibrated straight bridge wire, tunable headphone and an audio-oscillator consisting of a tuning fork giving a constant frequency of 1000 cycles per second and which can be worked by a six volt battery.

Air condenser, the capacity of which could be varied, was used for balancing the capacities and inductions in the various arms as well as in the resistances in the bridge, to overcome electrode effect and to aid in producing a definite and easily determined minimum sound in the telephone.

The cell constant was found to be 0.02720 and did not vary with temperatures. The cell constant was checked from time to time.

Bhattacharya and Nakhate's (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 1, 99) method was followed in preparing the solutions.

Results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

The variation of specific conductivity with temperature.

Solute.	Conc. (g./100 g.)	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	
		Solvent = Acetone.					
Benzoic acid	52.54	6.762	7.074	7.420	7.781	8.010	} × 10 ⁻⁷
	72.41			6.541	6.931	7.201	
Salicylic acid	48.47	1.051	1.752	1.823	1.914	1.982	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	70.33			1.855	1.962	2.066	
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	74.01	4.578	4.936	5.313	5.675	6.053	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	113.00			4.211	4.594	4.922	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	50.22	1.713	1.822	1.932	2.031	2.116	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	98.91			1.747	1.963	2.095	
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	70.50	4.365	4.699	4.930	5.310	5.570	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	101.20			5.450	5.794	6.043	
Cinnamic acid	38.05		9.772	10.320	10.800	11.190	} × 10 ⁻⁷
	48.78			10.960	11.500		
Phthalic acid	6.47		8.718	9.142	9.575	9.832	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	7.33			14.640	15.240	15.790	
Oxalic acid	32.10	18.130	19.370	20.810	22.140	23.470	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	38.56			21.150	22.820	24.700	
Succinic acid	3.27	2.408	2.494	2.566	2.630	2.671	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	6.868			4.148	4.276	4.393	
Solvent = MeOH.							
Benzoic acid	77.03	3.769	4.066	4.393	4.790	5.156	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	95.16			3.795	4.128	4.430	
Salicylic acid	64.36	3.020	3.310	3.642	3.902	4.230	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	74.15			3.176	3.475	3.780	
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	81.91	4.456	4.820	5.196	5.570	5.940	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	113.00			3.908	4.210	4.594	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	73.03	1.456	1.615	1.801	1.978	2.172	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	101.80			1.924	1.755	1.596	
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	53.65		6.247	6.533	6.724	6.933	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	68.21			6.860	6.860	7.112	
Cinnamic acid	33.54	0.802	0.872	0.939	1.009	1.152	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	40.40			0.739	0.805	0.879	
Phthalic acid	27.81	4.133	4.677	5.270	5.947	6.540	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	44.40			5.045	5.630	6.306	

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Conc.	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
Solvent = Propyl alcohol.						
Benzoic acid	32.53	1.859	2.034	2.189	2.383	2.554
	65.40		1.599	1.710	1.802	1.918
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	60.93	1.428	1.622	1.828	2.031	2.248
	94.74		1.497	1.724	1.940	2.154
Cinnamic acid	22.19	5.922	6.511	7.158	7.720	8.280
	33.15		6.410	7.158	7.759	8.461
Phthalic acid	7.25	2.697	3.092	3.497	3.874	4.273
	11.00		3.182	3.593	4.077	4.547
Succinic acid	4.92	6.610	7.381	8.155	8.876	9.726
	9.490		9.726	10.680	11.850	13.200
Solvent = Butyl alcohol.						
Salicylic acid	22.72	6.334	7.075	7.715	8.206	8.786
	33.25		7.047	8.565	9.261	9.852
Solvent = <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol.						
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	20.77	7.755	8.253	9.156	9.592	9.970
	46.93		10.400	11.330	12.220	13.220
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	18.10	2.981	3.294	3.407	3.608	3.923
	26.14			3.857	4.090	4.344
Cinnamic acid	8.32		2.063	2.293	2.557	2.761
	15.22			2.575	2.800	3.072
Phthalic acid	4.25	1.159	1.273	1.385	1.494	1.614
	10.60			1.828	2.091	2.324
Succinic acid	2.62		2.442	2.071	2.883	3.115
	5.61			4.337	4.655	5.010

NOTE: Specific conductivity has been determined at five different temperatures but due to brevity of space it is given at two different temperatures.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Table I specific conductivity has been plotted against temperature. The results obtained from the plot of $\mu-t$ can be divided into two categories. In the first category, we have put the systems which give a straight line plot for $\mu-t$, e. g. acetone-*o*-aminobenzoic acid, acetone-salicylic acid, methyl alcohol-*m*-nitrobenzoic acid, propyl alcohol-succinic acid, etc. and therefore these solutions obey the Walden equation,

$$\mu t = \mu_0 (1 + \alpha t) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

within the temperature range studied here. It may be pointed out that no abrupt change occurs in the plot of $\mu-t$ when the solution passes from the saturated to the supersaturated region.

The solutions in the second category, e. g. propyl alcohol-*m*-nitrobenzoic acid, propyl alcohol-benzoic acid, methyl alcohol-benzoic acid, acetone-phthalic acid, etc., do not obey Walden's equation and curvature is observed in the plot of $\mu-t$ for these solutions. These solutions probably obey the equation of Kohlrausch

$$\mu_t = \mu_o (1 + \alpha t + \beta t^2) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Relation between Conductivity and Viscosity.—In the case of plot of $\log \mu-1/T$ (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 78) we obtained straight line plots for the solutions in acetone, propyl and butyl alcohols, but the plots for $\log \mu-1/T$ for the solutions in methyl alcohol were generally not a straight line. Whereas in the case of plot of $\mu-t$, solutions in methyl alcohol generally give straight line plots but the solutions in acetone, propyl and butyl alcohols do not give a straight line plot. In the case of solutions in methyl alcohol the linearity for the plot of $\mu-t$, is more marked probably due to a higher value of dielectric constant of methyl alcohol than propyl and butyl alcohols where the dielectric constant is low, and so the conductivity is also low. Generally, when the conductivity is low, the plot of $\mu-t$ is not a straight line, e. g. in the case of the solution of benzoic acid in methyl alcohol.

Although no exact relationship between the conductivity and structure of the acids can be obtained, as the concentrations studied for the different solutions are different, but a qualitative idea can be obtained from a consideration of the results given in Table I.

If we compare the results for the specific conductivity for the solutions of different solvents and the same solute, it is observed that the conductivity of solutions in methyl alcohol is more than that of the solutions in propyl and butyl alcohols. This is due to the fact that the dielectric constant of methyl alcohol is 31.2, that of propyl alcohol is 22.2 and butyl alcohol, 19.2. Conductivity of methyl alcohol solutions is about 100 times more than that of propyl alcohol solutions, but there is not much difference between the values of conductivity for the solutions of propyl and butyl alcohols. e. g. conductivity of succinic acid in propyl alcohol is twice than that of butyl alcohol. As has been pointed out by Hunt and Briscoe (*loc. cit.*) this may be due to the fact that the separation of a methyl group from a hydroxyl group, i. e. OH by a CH₂ group does not alter the value of specific conductivity much, but the insertion of the second CH₂ group changes the conductivity values quite appreciably.

The conductivity of the solutions in acetone is equal to that of the solutions in propyl and butyl alcohols although the dielectric constant of acetone is 20.7 and is nearly equal to the dielectric constant of butyl and propyl alcohols, but the viscosity of acetone is very much less than these two alcohols. According to the above values of viscosity and dielectric constant, the conductivity of acetone solutions should have been higher than the solutions in butyl and propyl alcohols, but it is not so. No explanation is yet possible for these results.

It has been observed that the substitution of OH, NO₂ and NH₂ group in benzoic acid increases the conductivity of benzoic acid progressively. The effect of NH₂ group is more than NO₂ group, which is more than OH group for the solutions in methyl, propyl and butyl alcohols and acetone. Similar results have been obtained for the molecular conductivities of these acids in ethyl alcohol by Hunt and Briscoe (*loc. cit.*).

Conductivity of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid in methyl alcohol and acetone is more than that of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid solutions in these two solvents. Results have been explained by Briscoe and Hunt on the basis of the electronic theory of valence and current theories of molecular structure.

One of us (A. N. B.) is thankful to the Scientific Research Grant Committee, U. P. for the grant of a Research Fellowship.

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Received November 9, 1949.

A NOTE ON THE ISOLATION OF SAKURANIN, A GLUCOSIDE FROM THE BARK OF *PRUNUS PUDDUM* (N. O. ROSACEAE)

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The stem bark of *Prunus Puddum* has been shown in this laboratory to contain a flavone, Puddumetin, which has been shown to be identical with Genkwanin (7-methoxy-5:4'-dihydroxyflavone; Chakravarti and Ghose, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 171), a flavone, Sakuranetin (7-methoxy-5:4'-dihydroxyflavone; Chakravarti, Kundu and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 329) and an isoflavone, which has been named Prunusetin (Chakravarti and Bhar, *ibid.*, 1945, 22, 301).

Though this work is being continued in this laboratory for more than five years, recently Narasimhachari and Seshadri (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30, A, 271) have published a paper in this line and hence it is necessary to put on record our observations.

The note describes the isolation of another component from the bark of *Prunus Puddum*, the glucoside Sakuranin, which was isolated by Asahina, Shinoda and Inubuse